

Interview (stage 1_In development team)

1. (Team Work Management) - Survey Results Review

We got a low score about “including the safety expert’s opinion, management rarely changes the team’s priorities during an iteration.”

Opening Question

- Could you recall, if the survey results are the same with yours?
- Tell me about your observation.

Intermediate Question

- Could I ask you the reasons about why including the safety expert’s opinion, the management changed the team’s priorities during the iteration?
- If the safety expert’s opinion could change the team’s priorities during the iteration?
- If there are some priority between the safety user stories and the functional user stories? And Why?

Ending Question

- What do you think are the most effective ways to support your suggestions?
- Do you think there are some difficulties to execute the methods?
- What other positive issues can be contributed through this change?
- What other negative issues can be brought through this change?
- Is there something else you think I should know to understand?
- Is there anything you would like to ask me?

2. (Communication) - Survey Results Review

Based on the survey results, there is a conflict between the static data: The team communicate in a high-bandwidth manner, however, there is still a knowledge gap when someone goes on vacation.

Opening Question

- Do you think that these results can represent your opinion?
- If not, what is your opinion?
- Tell me about your observation?

Intermediate Question

- Could I ask you the reasons you think about this conflict?
- How are your feelings about the more communication chances in agile methods?
- What positive issues can you get from the communication?
- What do you think is the wrong style of communication?

Ending Question

- What do you think is the most effective way to solve this kind of conflict?
- If there are some negative influence of the method?
- What other positive issues can be contributed through this change?
- What other negative issues can be brought through this change?
- Is there something else you think I should know to understand?
- Is there anything you would like to ask me?

3. **(Requirements Emergency)** - Survey Results Review

Survey result is safety requirements are determined not early enough to appropriately influence design and testing.

Opening Question

- Does this answer represent your thought?
- What is your observations?

Intermediate Question

- What do you think is the reason about this phenomenon, which makes the safety requirements not early enough to be determined?
- Does this phenomenon happen throughout the sprint or just at the beginning of each iteration?
- What kinds of effect will occur because of the not early safety requirements?

Ending Question

- What do you think is the best way to solve this problem?
- How early should be enough to appropriately design and testing?
- How detail should be the safety requirements?
- What other positive issues can be contributed through this change?
- What other negative issues can be brought through this change?
- Is there something else you think I should know to understand?
- Is there anything you would like to ask me?

4. **(planning level)** - Survey Results Review

Not good about the safety expert performs a draft safety plan before each sprint, and the safety plan is detailed during each iteration in parallel with the development team.

Opening Questions

- Does this result represent your thought?
- What is your concrete observation?

Intermediate Questions

- What do you think is the main reasons that cause this result?

Ending Questions

- How detail and what kind of draft safety plan would be helpful before each sprint?
- Do you think there are other organization work needed to perform the draft safety plan?
- How to execute the safety plan?
- How detailed should be the safety plan during each iteration?
- How to execute the detailed safety plan in parallel with the development team?
- What other positive issues can be contributed through this change?
- What other negative issues can be brought through this change?
- Is there something else you think I should know to understand?
- Is there anything you would like to ask me?

5. **(When do we plan)** - Survey Results Review

Opening Questions

Up front planning for safety is being excessive.

- Does this result represent your thought?
- What is your concrete observation?

Intermediate Questions

- What do you think is the main reasons that cause this result?

Ending Questions

- When do you think is the best time to perform up front planning for safety?
- If there are some possibilities or difficulties to extend the time to perform up front planning for safety?
- How should we deal with this occasion?
- What other positive issues can be contributed through this change?
- What other negative issues can be brought through this change?
- Is there something else you think I should know to understand?
- Is there anything you would like to ask me?

6. **(Progress Tracking)** - Survey Results Review

Each safety feature doesn't have a well-defined completion criteria that can be used to determine if the safety feature is done or not done. We do not consider a partially completed feature done.

Opening Questions

- Does this result represent your thought?
- What is your concrete observation?

Intermediate Questions

- What do you think is the main reasons that cause this result?
- If each safety feature should be determined to be done?
- What are the difficulties to determine that the safety feature is done?

Ending Questions

- What kinds of the completion criteria could be determined as well-defined?
- What do you think that we can do when some safety features are difficult to decide a well-defined criteria?
- When is it better to decide the safety features' criteria?
- How to decide the safety features' criteria?
- Who is better to decide the safety features' criteria?
- What other positive issues can be contributed through this change?
- What other negative issues can be brought through this change?
- Is there something else you think I should know to understand?
- Is there anything you would like to ask me?